

Enhancing Intersection Navigation for Autonomous Vehicles: A Blockchain-Inspired Hash-Based Identification Approach

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Abstract—The rapid advancement and deployment of Autonomous Vehicles (AVs) necessitate innovative solutions for reliable and efficient navigation. In this context, a crucial aspect is the unequivocal identification of intersections. This paper proposes a novel methodology for uniquely identifying intersections by applying a hash algorithm that generates a distinct fingerprint of each intersection, inspired by the operational mechanisms within blockchain platforms, particularly mimicking the generation of Transaction Hashes. The solution's core is creating a hash tree to unequivocally identify the intersection for the AVs' navigation. The application to a real complex case study shows the applicability of the proposed approach.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement and deployment of Autonomous Vehicles (AVs) need to develop efficient strategies for uniquely identifying intersections [1]. The complexity of road networks, particularly in urban macro centers and especially in intersection areas, represents a challenge for current [2] map matching algorithms. Furthermore, in the context of intersection management and Autonomous Intersection Management (AIM), the problem arises of potential conflicts between AVs that may erroneously agree on the same intersection, being instead at different intersections, for example, overlapping.

GPS alone is insufficient for robust AV navigation in cities. Indeed, urban structures like tall buildings and tunnels degrade GPS accuracy through occlusion and multipath interference, producing localization errors exceeding 20 meters—over four times the 5 meter precision in ideal conditions. Such significant discrepancies between actual and estimated positions compromise autonomous driving safety and GPS outages from tunnels and underground streets also disrupt urban operations [3].

In recent years, the rapid development of AVs has led to a growing research interest in algorithms and related technologies. Chang and Shih [4] proposed an Intersection Location Service (ILS). This hash-based distributed location service algorithm exploits the characteristics of road intersections and the Chord algorithm as a location query and fault tolerance mechanism. In this study, ILS is compared with two well-known location service algorithms, grid location service and hierarchical location service, showing good performance regarding query success ratios and remarkable scalability

concerning network size. Gao et al. [5] studied autonomous car vision systems, focusing on automatically detecting and classifying road contexts and traffic intersections under different weather conditions. However, despite the attention to details of the road context, their work does not provide a specific solution for the unique identification of intersections.

Connected Autonomous Vehicles (CAVs) intersection management is outlined in a comprehensive survey by Khayatian et al. [6]. The study discusses key facets of real-world intersection management strategy development, including intersection management interfaces, vehicle scheduling policies, wireless technologies, and critical conflict detection.

Although these studies have contributed significantly to the research in this field, there remains a gap in solving the problem of the unique identification of intersections.

In the related literature reviews [7], blockchain is viewed mainly as an enabler for secure vehicular communication, decentralized data management, payments, and other Internet of Vehicles applications. However, blockchain-inspired solutions were never provided for detecting and identifying road intersections. Although spatial hashing techniques are effective for collision detection and may have great applicability for intersection identification [8], there is still ample space for further research in this area.

To fill this gap, we propose a novel approach that employs blockchain-inspired hash algorithms to identify intersections uniquely. In particular, this technique applies a hash algorithm to the intersection data, producing a unique fingerprint of the intersection itself. The proposed approach is inspired by the blockchain systems, where similar hash generation is used to create Transaction Hash and Block Hash.

The utilization of the proposed methodology is in a twofold manner: first, it allows the creation of a unique intersection footprint, enabling us to recall or uniquely identify the considered intersection in various contexts involving AVs. In line with recent developments in the management of AV intersections (e.g., [9], [10]), the proposed solution has the potential to contribute to more effective and safe intersection navigation.

Secondly, it is conceivable that, at the end of their routes, AVs could potentially notarize on the blockchain, through a specific transaction or within a particular smart contract, the decisions made at every intersection, thereby unambiguously identifying them. This approach could trigger dedicated actions or smart contracts within the blockchain, such as imposing penalties for crossing into a restricted traffic zone, as a future application possibility.

The remaining parts of the paper are organized as follows.

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Section II describes the problem and Section III proposes the hash-based solution. In addition, Section IV proposes a decentralized approach for hash generation and depicts the procedure for the AVs. Finally, Section V describes and discusses a case study and Section VI draws the conclusions.

II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

In the related literature, the AIM can be faced in centralized or decentralized approaches. In centralized AIM, vehicles communicate with an intersection manager to reserve conflict-free trajectories through the intersection space-time [11]. Overlapping or adjacent intersections create difficulties in delineating clear communication zone boundaries. Vehicles may interact with multiple intersection managers simultaneously or experience confusion determining which manager to contact [12]. Centralized approaches to combining nearby intersections into a single coordination zone have been explored but face drawbacks like single points of failure, infrastructure constraints, and limited scalability [13]. The decentralized AIM has advantages in robustness and flexibility, but ambiguities in intersection boundaries can lead to coordination and interpretation issues between vehicles [14].

The introduction of lane-free AIM schemes by Li et al. [15], where batch-processing frameworks leverage, points out the necessity of having a unique identifier for each intersection. In such dynamic environments where CAVs adjust their velocities and paths continuously and cooperatively within an intersection, the absence of a unique identifier can escalate the complexity of the batch coordination process. It might give rise to scenarios where batches from different intersections incorrectly intertwine due to the need for precise intersection delineations, leading to safety hazards and inefficiencies. As proposed in this paper, establishing a unique intersection hash would facilitate seamless batch processing by clearly defining the bounds of each intersection, thereby ensuring that the cooperative trajectory planning within each batch is confined to the correct intersection space.

Despite the challenges identified with both centralized and decentralized AIM systems, there has been a promising approach leveraged by Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) proposed by Isele et al. [16] to address the safety and efficiency in unsignaled intersections. Furthermore, integrating a unique intersection identification system, as proposed in this study, could work synergistically with DRL approaches, offering a more data-driven solution to navigate through intersections efficiently. Establishing a unique fingerprint for each intersection makes channeling more data into the DRL systems possible. This approach can simplify the learning processes and facilitate the application of the consensus protocols in real-world scenarios at intersections. Then, we face the problem of accurately identifying intersections and their associated communication zones in efficient AIM systems.

Code 1 Block Data

```

1 { "hash": "000000000000000001ca3f1c683b050242
2 df5842a20692515793b7c051b2b0f",
3 "height": 571119,
4 [...] "merkleroot": "9f217be3a492ebbab53fb207
5 092204f1cb8530ae1144038848e8db044862ea53",
6 "tx": [
7 "a654a7f137b660d4d36973084c34d152e1e1970ec
8 ee8753057c4936427171cf1",
9 [...],
10 "6a747d2b4c98bc7a8e510e6b50abd036553eeefe6
11 6c86633bf5ec7c444947e0b",
12 [...],
13 "be3728bb8cdbc0957fc6c600a094f34f521f09d46
14 b2c450009bc65cbabda1975"
15 ],
16 "nonce": 334061627,
17 "difficulty": 6393023717201.863,
18 "chainwork": "00000000000000000000000000000000
19 0000000005c7966f5de524c504466f30",
20 "nTx": 2100,
21 "previousblockhash": "000000000000000002770
22 3744d8d484a7fda73a16cd88af92fab3ea6f9d297" }

```

III. HASH-BASED SOLUTION

A. Inspirations from the Blockchain: The Role of Hash Algorithms

Satoshi Nakamoto, in 2009, already made extensive use of hash algorithms to uniquely identify transactions within his blockchain and subsequently to identify each block uniquely [17]. Hash algorithms are cryptographic functions that input data of any size and output a fixed-length string. This string is essentially a unique "fingerprint" of the original data. A key feature of hash algorithms is that even a small change to the input data produces an entirely different hash. This makes hash algorithms extremely useful for verifying data integrity [18], [19].

The Code 1 shows block 571119's raw code of the Bitcoin blockchain. Note that all transactions included within this specific block are reported as a hash, where a654a7[...]7171cf1 is the hash of the first one and be3728[...]bda1975 is the hash of the last transaction included in the block. Along with the transactions in the block, a series of collateral information is also inserted into the block, including the previous block's hash. With this method, the Bitcoin blockchain uniquely identifies blocks and individual transactions.

In cryptographic theory, it is recognized that alterations to a given piece of information invariably result in a corresponding change to its hash. A slight modification in the input, even a change as minor as flipping a single bit, leads to a significant alteration in the output hash, a phenomenon commonly known as the "avalanche effect". This property is critical in numerous applications of hash functions, including digital signatures, integrity checks, and password security, among others. This sensitivity to input data contributes to the robustness of hash functions in detecting tampering or corruption in the original information [20], [21].

B. Proposed Solution

There is a consensus among researchers that GPS alone does not provide sufficient accuracy for autonomous vehicle navigation [22], [23].

TABLE I
ATTRIBUTES OF THE INTERSECTION DATA JSON OBJECT

Key	Type	Description
location	Object	An object containing the geographical coordinates of the intersection.
├ latitude	Number	The latitude of the intersection, in decimal degrees.
├ longitude	Number	The longitude of the intersection, in decimal degrees.
└ altitude	Number	The altitude of the intersection, in meters above sea level.
toponymy	Object	An object containing the names associated with the intersection.
├ streetNames	Array of Strings	A list containing the various names that refer to the intersection.
└ language	String	The ISO 639-1 code of the language set in the Navigation System
parameters	Object	An object containing details describing the characteristics of the intersection.
├ streetCount	Number	The number of streets intersecting at the intersection.
└ trafficLights	Boolean	A boolean indicating the presence of traffic lights at the intersection.

Pal et al. [24] proposed recording the locations of traffic signs in a database and then using the database to complement GPS and sensor data in autonomous vehicles. Inspired by this approach, we build a *JavaScript Object Notation* (JSON) object that could be replicated deterministically and straightforwardly. Since a JSON object is a collection of key-value pairs, where the "value" can be a number, a string, a Boolean, an array, or even another JSON object, we choose to include in the JSON the attributes depicted in Table I to identify an intersection uniquely. This allows us to nest three different JSON objects within the identifying data of our intersection (*location*, *toponymy* and *parameters*).

A critical issue is determining the level of accuracy required for GPS coordinates since excessive precision could generate different hashes. In this approach, excessive precision by the GPS device could be a problem since two vehicles within the same smaller roundabout, even just being at two different points, could produce two different hashes. To address this problem, it must be taken into account that within GPS coordinates one degree without decimal places has an approximation of about 111 km [25], three decimal places offer an accuracy of 111 meters and four decimal places offer an accuracy of 11 meters. Since GPS is not the only tool for the univocal identification of the intersection, it was chosen to approximate it up to three digits. The same approach has been used for the altitude.

Utilizing the attributes of the intersection to create a

JSON object, the decision to process it through the SHA256 algorithm was determined after carefully considering the prevalent SHA-256, part of the SHA-2 family, over SHA-3 alternatives. Despite the potentially higher security of SHA-3 options, SHA-256 was favored due to its demonstrated stability, uniqueness of the results with the same inputs and uniform and rapid processing capabilities unaffected by input size variations [26].

Algorithm 1 specifies the JSON objects that are defined using the dictionary data structure in Python, which closely aligns with the conventions of JSON. Here, we choose to produce the hashes of the single JSON-child objects to use them separately.

Algorithm 1 Hashing JSON Object Children

```

1: procedure HASHJSONOBJECTS(obj)
2:   child1, child2, child3  $\leftarrow$  ExtractChildren(obj)
3:    $\triangleright$  Extract the three JSON child objects
4:   for  $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$  do
5:     jsonStringi  $\leftarrow$  SortAndStringify(childi)
6:      $\triangleright$  Convert the  $i$ -th JSON object to a sorted string
7:     encodedStringi  $\leftarrow$  Encode(jsonStringi)
8:      $\triangleright$  Encode the  $i$ -th JSON string
9:     hashi  $\leftarrow$  InitializeHash("SHA-256")
10:     $\triangleright$  Initialize a new SHA-256 hash object for the  $i$ -th
        child
11:    Update(hashi, encodedStringi)
12:     $\triangleright$  Update the  $i$ -th hash with the encoded JSON string
13:    hashedJsoni  $\leftarrow$  Finalize(hashi)
14:     $\triangleright$  Convert the  $i$ -th hash to a hexadecimal string
15:  return hashedJson1, hashedJson2, hashedJson3

```

Following the execution of Algorithm 1, each JSON child object is individually processed through a series of transformations to obtain their SHA-256 hash representations eventually.

Firstly, the *SortAndStringify* function (Step 4) is utilized, which internally leverages Python's `json.dumps()` function with the `sort_keys=True` parameter. This ensures a consistent, ordered serialization of the dictionary entries, a crucial aspect given that the SHA-256 hashing algorithm operates sequentially on the input data; different ordering would result in distinct hashes. This function can also include other normalization parameters, such as avoiding capital letters or replacing toponymic abbreviations. Subsequently, the sorted JSON strings are encoded into UTF-8 format through the *Encode* function (Step 5). This transformation is indispensable, as the *InitializeHash* function, used in the next step, mandates bytes-like objects as input rather than plain strings. In Step 6, a new SHA-256 hash object is initialized for each child using Python's `hashlib.sha256()` function, following which the hash objects are updated with the encoded JSON strings through the *Update* function (Step 7). Finally, the SHA-256 hash objects are converted to their hexadecimal string representations using the *Finalize* function (Step 8). This function utilizes the `hexdigest()` method to transform

the binary hash data into a hexadecimal string, facilitating easy readability and further analytical processing. Through this structured approach, the algorithm ensures the consistent and reliable hashing of JSON object children, readying them for subsequent use or analysis.

To obtain the unique identifier of the entire intersection, the path to follow is not the creation of the hash of the JSON as a whole object but rather the result of the hash of the hashes of the child JSON, making a Merkle Tree. A *Merkle Tree* is a hash-based data structure that generalizes the hash list. It is a tree structure in which each leaf node is a hash of a block of data, and each non-leaf node is a hash of its children [27], [28]. Particularly when dealing with complex JSON objects that encompass multiple keys such as "location", "toponymy", and "parameters", a Merkle Tree allows granular integrity checks. Each key-value pair can be hashed individually to form leaf nodes in the tree, enabling rapid and resource-efficient verification of sub-components of the data. This hierarchical structure facilitates pinpointing discrepancies down to specific keys, obviating the need to traverse or verify the entire dataset. At that point, the AV can check whether the hashes of the smaller objects match or not and where the discrepancies are. By doing this, we establish that the threshold to be respected is that 2/3 of the child hashes must match.

IV. INTERSECTION IDENTIFICATION FOR AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES

This section provides a tool for mitigating the problems that can occur when autonomous vehicles have to cross an intersection.

In the related literature ([9], [10], [29]), the intersection is divided into two zones: the Control Zone (CZ), where the vehicles communicate to find an agreement about the order by which they get through the intersection, and the Merging Zone (MZ), where the collisions can occur.

The generation of a hash that identifies the intersection allows the vehicles to unequivocally identify the intersection before entering the CZ to guarantee that the autonomous vehicles communicate with the vehicles involved in the same intersection.

To avoid single points of failure within the system and to increase scalability and flexibility, we adopted a decentralized approach, so the vehicle can calculate the hashes of the intersections when planning the route, verifying them and proceeding when all the vehicles approaching the intersection agree on the identifier of the crossing they are facing.

Algorithm 2 reports the steps the autonomous vehicles can perform.

As the vehicle approaches an intersection, it uses the `ApproachControlZone(intersection)` function to enter the designated control zone. Within this zone, the vehicle utilizes the `CollectDataAndRecheckHash(zone)` function to harvest real-time data and recompute the hash accordingly. This fetches the necessary data and validates the hash, thus ensuring a secure traversal through the intersection. A consensus mechanism is instituted, wherein

Algorithm 2 Procedure of Autonomous Vehicle

```

1: procedure AUTONOMOUSVEHICLEPROCEDURE
2:   route ← DefineRoute()           ▷ Define route
3:   path ← CalculatePath(route)     ▷ Get path
4:   intersections ← IdentifyIntersections(path)
5:                                       ▷ Find intersections
6:   hashes ← Calc.IntersectionsHashes(intersections)
7:                                       ▷ Get hashes
8:   StartJourney(path)
9:   for each intersection in intersections do
10:    zone ← ApproachControlZone(intersection)
11:    data, hash ← CollectDataAndRecheckHash(zone)
12:                                       ▷ Get data and recheck hash
13:    consensus ← ExchangeHash(hash, hashes)
14:    if not consensus then
15:      childHashes ← GetChildHashes(data)
16:      consensus ← ExchangeChildHashes(childHashes)
17:                                       ▷ 2/3 consensus
18:      if not consensus then
19:        FallbackToOriginalConsensus()
20:        FollowConsensus()
21:    ReachDestination()
22:    UploadToBlockchain(hashes)     ▷ Upload data

```

the newly obtained hash is exchanged with other vehicles in the vicinity using the `ExchangeHash(hash, hashes)` function. If a consensus isn't achieved, then a secondary level of consensus is sought by exchanging child hashes, which have a more granular data management. This strategy needs at least a 2/3 agreement via the `ExchangeChildHashes(childHashes)` function. If consensus remains elusive, the procedure reverts to the original consensus mechanism through the `FallbackToOriginalConsensus()` function, ensuring navigation continuity while maintaining safety. Regardless of the path to achieving consensus, the `FollowConsensus()` function directs the vehicle to adhere to the agreed consensus.

V. CASE STUDY

A. Case study description

In this section, we show an application of the proposed solution to a real complex case study: the *Magic Roundabout* in Swindon, England formed by an unconventional multi-roundabout configuration as illustrated in Fig. 1. With five satellite roundabouts encircling a central hub, identifying the correct pathway through this complex traffic circle is non-trivial compared to traditional single-ring layouts.

Several factors contribute to the difficulty autonomous vehicles face when approaching this particular roundabout:

- The unusual arrangement of alternating clockwise and counter-clockwise flows across multiple intersections introduces ambiguity in determining the appropriate

Fig. 1. Map view of the "Magic Roundabout" in Swindon, England (UK) [30]

yielding behavior. Unlike single roundabouts where the right-of-way is clear, the crisscrossing of traffic directions at the Magic Roundabout leads to confusion.

- Occlusions from infrastructure and other vehicles can obstruct sensor visibility. With multiple intersections in close proximity, obstructions are more likely to prevent early detection of crossing traffic flows.
- The complexity makes a priori mapping of valid trajectories difficult. Predefined driving routes are less effective since the environment is highly dynamic.
- Close proximity of entry and exit points creates uncertainty in intersection identification. Determining which specific roundabout an autonomous vehicle should target is obscured by near parallel roads.

B. Proposed Solution

The considered Magic Roundabout is divided into a set of sections as illustrated in Fig. 2, and each section represents a roundabout and is denoted with a different color. We focus on two roundabouts, named **Blue** and **Pink**. These roundabouts are characterized by unique features, ensuring their unequivocal identification. In particular, this precise identification is attainable even under conditions where the GPS signal's accuracy, traditionally considered the primary source of location information, is compromised. This resilience is due to the inclusion of additional data stored securely within the individual JSON objects corresponding to each roundabout. Essentially, each roundabout is seen as an independent entity possessing its unique data.

After obtaining the unique hash derived from the JSON objects, the vehicles initiate a data-sharing protocol with the other vehicles circulating within the *Magic Roundabout*. This protocol provides these vehicles with access to accurate, real-time data regarding the behavior and movement of vehicles within the smaller roundabouts.

For instance, a vehicle traveling on the A 4259 and wishing to continue on it, will approach this junction by first crossing the **Pink roundabout**, then the **Cyan roundabout** and finally the **Blue roundabout**. Then, the vehicle communicates its movements to all the present vehicles, identifying precisely which sections of the macro roundabout it will face at

Fig. 2. Control Zones intersections on *Swindon Magic Roundabout.svg* by *Hk knq* [31]

Code 2 Data of the **Blue** roundabout in 2 in JSON format.

```
1 {"location": {"latitude": 51.562, "longitude":
  -1.771, "altitude": 102},
2  "toponymy": {"streetNames": ["County Road", "
  Magic Roundabout", "Private Road", "A 4259"
  ], "Language": "en"},
3  "parameters": {"streetCount": 4, "trafficLights
  ": false}}
```

each time interval. This allows it to negotiate the intersection simultaneously with vehicles that do not need the smaller roundabouts it uses in the same time interval.

In the following, we describe the distinguishing features of the JSON objects associated with the two roundabouts **Blue** and **Pink** that are determined by Code 2 and Code 3, respectively.

According to Algorithm 1, the SHA-256 hash of the JSON object representing the **Blue** and the **Pink** roundabout are represented in Table II where, for brevity, only the first hash is reported.

Code 3 Data of the **Pink** roundabout in 2 in JSON format.

```
1 {"location": {"latitude": 51.562, "longitude":
  -1.771, "altitude": 101},
2  "toponymy": {"streetNames": ["A 4259", "Magic
  Roundabout", "Queen's Drive"], "Language": "
  en"},
3  "parameters": {"streetCount": 3, "trafficLights
  ": false}}
```

Drawing parallels with operational protocols in the context of blockchain systems, our approach can be compared to the methodology employed within a Bitcoin block. In such a system, each transaction is represented not by its specific details, but through a unique hash that encapsulates all the requisite information. Likewise, according to the Merkle Tree structure, a unique identifier could be assigned to the entire roundabout, which is a composite hash computed by aggregating the hashes of all the smaller roundabouts (Blue, Cyan, Pink, etc.).

Following the construction of the Merkle Tree, the hash of the **Blue** roundabout is "82fb8b6622ae104f323ed77d7a35ff120362f7d8f257a7822f185e67b460f2c8" and the hash of the

TABLE II

COMPUTED SHA-256 HASHES FOR THE CHILD OBJECTS IN THE BLUE AND PINK JSON REPRESENTATIONS

JSON Object	JSON-child	SHA-256 Hash
Blue	location	7b01cba7acb9b65b4b726289d6664e19be31e243beba38491de16dd16f610ec6
	toponymy parameters	275b8a67be3[...]f3c09784e1b05ad4e76a62[...]52ad6a4d1b7
Pink	location	a3d51bacbb3[...]7e2733b96b7
	toponymy parameters	607a69ded6d[...]68bab948a4c062bf46d1d7[...]f5db03f0d16

Pink one is "cce096295cfe607badb2a37c6a34c9584e78f5720ba678b17ff2e66df3726502".

C. Discussion of the results and critical issues analysis

The proposed approach allows us to divide a very complex intersection with a huge Control Zone (CZ) into smaller and more manageable intersections. Although these new CZs overlap, each one is distinctly identified, thereby accelerating the consensus-reaching process for approaching vehicles.

The considered case study has an overall circumference of approximately 100 meters. Therefore, given how the system has been devised, every single argument of the JSON object does not need to be unique, given that the uniqueness of the object is given by the sum of the elements it contains and not by the single data. So, even if we choose to cut the GPS coordinates at 3 digits, having two small roundabouts utterly identical regarding GPS coordinates, the identification hashes will still be unique.

An additional problem that can occur is the nomenclature of the streets. For example, having two systems in different languages could produce slightly different input data; e.g., it could happen if a vehicle with the Latin alphabet generated the unique identifiers of Greek road junctions, which local cars identify with the Greek alphabet. The "toponymy" child hash match could be deprioritized to resolve this issue so that other data are preferred. It should also be noted that the number of child objects within the JSON can be enriched or modified depending on particular needs.

The use of the unique identification of the intersections, in addition to allowing the navigation of autonomous vehicles with greater precision, can provide additional application scenarios. For example, remaining in the blockchain realm, our solution can be used to notarize the route taken by the autonomous vehicle during the journey or during the day. This information, being uniquely notarized on the blockchain, would also allow the resolution of road disputes based on the uncertainty of the data.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper leveraged features inspired by blockchain technology, specifically employing hash algorithms such as SHA-256, to make a significant advancement in the unambiguous identification of road intersections, a critical aspect in

the advancement of autonomous vehicle (AV) technologies. With this approach, intersections can now be distinguished unequivocally, based on their unique characteristics, thereby enhancing resilience against inaccuracies inherent in GPS technology. This development ensures that robust identification remains feasible even when the GPS signal fidelity is compromised. The outcome is a granular communication mechanism whereby vehicles can seamlessly communicate intricate operational details at every single intersection, no matter how close or overlapped they are. We described a methodology to assign a unique identifier to each intersection. This assures uninterrupted data flow and, consequently, augmented traffic management efficacy. Moreover, the delineation of Control Zones facilitates swift consensus among vehicles, even amidst visual barriers. The efficacy of this approach is evidenced in the proposed case study, showing the practical applicability of the proposed solution. In future research, we plan to use Artificial Intelligence to draw a basic pattern of the crossing and hash the derived image composed only of uniquely raw geometric shapes.

REFERENCES

- [1] X. Xie, W. Liao, H. K. Aghajan, P. Veelaert, and W. Philips, "Detecting road intersections from gps traces using longest common subsequence algorithm," *ISPRS Int. J. Geo Inf.*, vol. 6, p. 1, 2016.
- [2] W. Liao, W. Lv, T. Zhu, and D. Wu, "A map matching algorithm for intersections based on Floating Car Data," in *2008 10th International Conference on Advanced Communication Technology*, IEEE, 2 2008.
- [3] T. Matsushita, T. Tanaka, and M. Yonekawa, "Method for accuracy improvement of gps measurement in the city," in *2009 ICCAS-SICE*, pp. 3966–3969, Aug 2009.
- [4] Y.-J. Chang and T. L. Shih, "Intersection location service and performance comparison of three location service algorithms for vehicular ad hoc networks in city environments," in *2008 3rd International Symposium on Wireless Pervasive Computing*, pp. 562–565, May 2008.
- [5] J. Gao, D. Wang, C.-P. Lin, C. Luo, Y. Ruan, and M. Yuan, "Detecting and learning city intersection traffic contexts for autonomous vehicles," *Journal of Smart Cities and Society*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 213–239, 2022.
- [6] M. Khayatian, M. Mehrabian, E. Andert, R. Dedinsky, S. Choudhary, Y. Lou, and A. Shrivastava, "A survey on intersection management of connected autonomous vehicles," *ACM Transactions on Cyber-Physical Systems*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 1–27, 2020.
- [7] R. Jabbar, E. Dhib, A. B. Said, M. Krichen, N. Fetais, E. Zaidan, and K. Barkaoui, "Blockchain technology for intelligent transportation systems: A systematic literature review," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 20995–21031, 2022.
- [8] M. Eitz and G. Lixu, "Hierarchical Spatial Hashing for Real-time Collision Detection," in *IEEE International Conference on Shape Modeling and Applications 2007 (SMI '07)*, IEEE, 6 2007.
- [9] G. Difilippo, M. P. Fanti, and A. Marcello Mangini, "A consensus protocol for connecting automated vehicles at signal-free intersection," in *2022 IEEE 61st Conference on Decision and Control (CDC)*, pp. 6568–6573, Dec 2022.
- [10] F. Paparella, G. Volpe, A. M. Mangini, and M. P. Fanti, "Collision avoidance strategy for autonomous intersection management by a central optimizer algorithm," in *Accepted at The 2023 IEEE Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics*, 2023.
- [11] M. Hausknecht, T.-C. Au, and P. Stone, "Autonomous intersection management: Multi-intersection optimization," in *2011 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*, pp. 4581–4586, Sep. 2011.
- [12] Y. Li and Q. Liu, "Intersection management for autonomous vehicles with vehicle-to-infrastructure communication," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 15, pp. 1–12, 07 2020.
- [13] Z. Farkas, A. Mihály, and P. Gáspár, "Analysis of model predictive intersection control for autonomous vehicles," *Periodica Polytechnica Transportation Engineering*, vol. 51, no. 3, p. 209–215, 2023.

- [14] A. K. Ziliaskopoulos, S. T. Waller, Y. Li, and M. Byram, "Large-scale dynamic traffic assignment: Implementation issues and computational analysis," *Journal of Transportation Engineering*, vol. 130, no. 5, 2004.
- [15] B. Li, Y. Zhang, T. Acarman, Y. Ouyang, C. Yaman, and Y. Wang, "Lane-free autonomous intersection management: A batch-processing framework integrating reservation-based and planning-based methods," in *2021 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, pp. 7915–7921, May 2021.
- [16] D. Isele, R. Rahimi, A. Cosgun, K. Subramanian, and K. Fujimura, "Navigating occluded intersections with autonomous vehicles using deep reinforcement learning," in *2018 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, pp. 2034–2039, May 2018.
- [17] S. Nakamoto, "Bitcoin: A peer-to-peer electronic cash system," tech. rep., Bitcoin.org, 2008.
- [18] I. O. Epicoco, M. Pierro, and F. Sarzana Di Sant'ippolito, *Il diritto del metaverso - NFT, DeFi, GameFi e privacy*. Giappichelli, 12 2022.
- [19] S. P and K. Venkatesh, "An analysis of various techniques in blockchain applications," in *2022 6th International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Control Systems (ICICCS)*, pp. 857–860, May 2022.
- [20] N. Khairina, M. K. Harahap, and J. H. Lubis, "The Authenticity of Image using Hash MD5 and Steganography Least Significant Bit," *IJISTECH (International Journal Of Information System Technology)*, vol. 2, p. 1, nov 30 2018.
- [21] W. Gilpin, "Cryptographic hashing using chaotic hydrodynamics," *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, vol. 115, pp. 4869–4874, apr 23 2018.
- [22] Y. Dupuis, P. Merriaux, P. Subirats, R. Bouteau, X. Savatier, and P. Vasseur, "Gps-based preliminary map estimation for autonomous vehicle mission preparation," in *2014 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*, pp. 4241–4246, Sep. 2014.
- [23] H. Min, X. Wu, C. Cheng, and X. Zhao, "Kinematic and dynamic vehicle model-assisted global positioning method for autonomous vehicles with low-cost gps/camera/in-vehicle sensors," *Sensors*, vol. 19, no. 24, p. 5430, 2019.
- [24] M. Pál, F. Vörös, I. Elek, and B. Kovács, "Possibilities of high precision gps data in autonomous driving," *Abstracts of the ICA*, vol. 1, p. 286, 2019.
- [25] J. V. Sickle, *GPS for Land Surveyors*. CRC Press, 2001.
- [26] M. Padhi and R. Chaudhari, "An optimized pipelined architecture of sha-256 hash function," in *2017 7th International Symposium on Embedded Computing and System Design (ISED)*, pp. 1–4, Dec 2017.
- [27] R. C. Merkle, "A certified digital signature," in *Advances in Cryptology — CRYPTO' 89 Proceedings* (G. Brassard, ed.), (New York, NY), pp. 218–238, Springer New York, 1990.
- [28] A. Chumbley, K. Moore, and J. Khim, "Merkle tree." <https://brilliant.org/wiki/merkle-tree/>, 2023. Accessed: Sep. 14, 2023.
- [29] S. Adams and M. J. Rutherford, "Decentralized intersection management through peer-to-peer technology," in *2015 IEEE International Conference on Peer-to-Peer Computing (P2P)*, pp. 1–5, Sep. 2015.
- [30] "Magic roundabout in swindon, england." <https://goo.gl/maps/56kepQSZ8TbVr3LN6>, 2023. Accessed: Jul. 30, 2023.
- [31] H. kng, "Map of the magic roundabout in swindon." <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=9034460>, 01 2010. Accessed: Aug. 3, 2023.